

SURFACE RECONSTRUCTION OF A LANDSLIDE AFFECTED AREA USING GEOMORPHOLOGICAL GEOLOGICAL AND GEOPHYSICAL DATA

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Introduction

In this paper we explore the possibility of reconstructing the topography of a confined area which is subject to a continuous transformation, as proved by both geological observations as well as cartographical and geomorphological ones. The present relief is a result of combined action of external forces and noticeable internal ones as the area of study is positioned in the Carpathian orogen, at the tectonic contact between the Convolute Flysch nappe and the Macla nappe (both belonging to Moldavides system),

The topography reconstruction approach used in this paper is based on a method of calculating the volume eroded by the fluvial-torrential valleys and branched ravines. To determine the exact geometrical form of the cross-section of such valleys it is a rather difficult process in an area with fierce dynamic, such as the Ialomița Sub-Carpathians Region. The key element in the proposed modelling approach is to calculate the evacuated volume of the researched area and therefore to estimate the material removed by drainage erosion since that basin started to develop the actual form. In order to calculate the eroded volume it is necessary to estimate the initial landform.

The initial landform reconstruction as well the present landform evaluation was based on data retrieved from high-resolution topographical maps and Digital Elevation Models, constrains being applied by adding recent geomorphological field observations. The prediction resulted according to the proposed methodology is subsequently compared with estimation on the thickness of the dislocated material retrieved from recent geophysical measurements.

Methodology

The area of study is located in the sub-Carpathian space Fieni - Ialomița Valley, slightly upstream the confluence of the Ialomița with the western Ialomicioara. Developed in the Upper Pliocene - Quaternary, transverse to the basic tectonic-structural units (the Palogen flysch and the molasses) and to the folded structures (anticlinal and synclinal), the Ialomița River formed a wide corridor within this space, where the river meandered and folded in several arms; the slopes are moderately tilted and still maintain the levels of the first 2 terraces, most often affected by the current Geo-morphological processes: streams, ravines, landslides, surface erosion.

The reconstruction of the surfaces in the sub-Carpathian space Fieni-Ialomița Valley was a complex process that involved the analysis of data extracted from cartographic materials and correlated with observations in the field. We have generated both the hypsometric map of the current surface and the hypsometric map of the initial surface, both having as the landmark Măgura Bela Hill, with the homonym peak, 665.18m high (considered the oldest area where it began the formation of the current aspect of the area under study).

The reconstruction of the initial drainage surface is part of the methodology applied to find out the total fluvial erosion. The total fluvial erosion is obtained by calculating the evacuated volume of the researched sub-basins. The concept is based on the consideration that the volume of the negative shape of a sub-basin is approximately equivalent to the volume of the material removed by drainage erosion since that basin started to develop the actual form (Peguy, 1942; Popescu, 1986)

The quantitative evaluation of the erosion in a hydrographic basin, specific to a certain region, will deal with the parameters reflecting the intensity of the morphogenetic processes over a specified period of time (millions of years, in general) .

In order to obtain the eroded volume we subtract the volume of the present landform from the volume of the initial landform. The following steps were used to accomplish the task:

a) the demarcation of the hydrographic basin;

b) the hindcast of the contour line of the initial topographic surface (H_i) where the depression (deepening) of the valley network of the sub-Carpathian Ialomita River basin commenced (closely related to the neighboring basins due to a common evolution in the geological past) (Grecu, 1998); It actually means plotting some linear outlines to connect the valley mouth (level zero) to the peaks of the watersheds (remains of the initial topographic area); subsequently, by interpolation, the junction of the initial contour lines are identified, by associating into contours with same value. The orientation of such contours considers the beginning of a major unity pre-existent in the actual basin (for example, the inception of a versant of a valley, superior in value to the existent one);

c) the calculation of the initial landform volume (V_{ri}) and the present one (V_{ra}), by summing up the partial landform volumes (V_{rp}) between the surface of the contour line (S_c) and the accumulated relative height (DH_c) estimated in comparison with the minimum altitude on the thalweg (Fig. 1a; Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1 Recent surface of hydrographic basins in left-size of Ialomita-Fieni area (a), reconstruction of initial surface of hydrographic basins in left-size of Ialomita-Fieni area (b) and calculated differences (given as thickness) that occur inside the basin (c)

To assess the erosion only by measuring the thickness of the dislocated material was done as follows:

- dividing the hydrographic basin into modules with constant surface;
- calculating the average altitude of the present landform (H_{med}) for each charted surface;
- finding the thickens of the eroded material (G_{er}) of each surface;
- calculating the volume of the eroded material (V_{er}) for each unit of surface (S);
- finding the total eroded volume (V_{ter}) by summing up the partial volumes (V_{er}) of each unit of surface.

This method helps identifying differences that occur inside the basin (petrographic, tectonic, changes of the local level, etc) (Fig. 1c).

Results interpretation and conclusions

By superimposing the two maps (Fig. 1a and 1b) and the Geo-morphometric modelling, we have been able to chart the map of the eroded relief (Fig. 1c). These results were correlated with results from the geophysical profiles (Electrical Resistivity Tomography –ERT- measurements) executed on the left slope of the Ialomita, superimposed on Terrace 1 and, partially on Terrace 2. Details on the acquisition technique and ERT data interpretation are given in papers Chitea & Nutu-Dragomir, 2019 and Nutu-Dragomir & Chitea, 2019.

Fig. 2 Recent surface of hydrographic basins (a) and details for the central area division (b)

For a more complex analysis, cumulative hypsometric curves have been calculated for the sediment areas in the limitrophe areas (two side drainage basins and an interbinial space) (Fig. 2a). The correlations between the hypsometric curves corresponding to the initial and current surfaces, differ, as follows:

- for the Northern part of the basin (marked as N on Fig. 2a), oriented south-east - north-west, with an area of 14.54 ha, the relationship between the 2 curves is reversed, by obtaining an additional volume of about 22785 m³, ie an addition of 2% eroded material from the upper parts and deposited between altitudes of 510-620 m, most probably by surface erosion and shallow surface landslides.
- for the Southern part of the basin (marked as S on Fig. 2a), oriented east-west, with an area of 34.81 ha, with a slightly elongated shape, the relationship between the 2 curves indicates a direct relation, that is, the basin has lost a certain volume of material. At a closer look, especially after the morphometric modelling, we notice that the value of the overall volume resulting from the difference of the 2 curves is in favour of the current shape of the Southern basin (16059 m³). The explanation of this fact relies on the following: the shape of the basin is of “lobat” type. The surface is larger compared to the other basin, the slopes are actually symmetrical and the general inclination is from west to east, as a result of the distribution of the material and, consequently, the variations of the surfaces are uniform. Surface losses at the upper part of the basin are compensated by the surface gains at the bottom.
- the third area –central part of the basin (marked as C on Fig. 2a) is formed on the remains of the lower terraces, looking like deluge formations coming from the slopes, either by shuffling or by sliding.

The hypsometric curves (Fig. 3a,3b) for the “C” part of the basin (presented in a detailed form in Fig. 2b) shows an indirect relationship, that is, a surface gain on stages of relief and a surplus of volume in favour of the current shape of the area. With a current area of about 14.5 ha there has been a gain of volume and areas on relief stages. The volume increase of 28604 m³ is due to the action of the current Geo-morphological processes: shifts, landslides, floods, torrentiality, developed on an active new-tectonic background.

Fig. 3 Calculated cumulative hypsometric curves for profile A (a) and profile B from central part of the basin marked according to Fig. 2b and selected Electrical Resistivity Tomography section

The third basin was also studied by means of ERT measurements, down to 50m deep. The intersection of the divided sectors of this basin with the ERT profiles is marked on the present-day hypsometric curves (Fig. 3a and 3b). An example of ERT results is given in Fig. 3c. According to ERT results, there are significant lithological differences along this relative confined sector. The Northern part of ERT lines generally displays higher resistivity values, specific to highly porous and moistured sandstones or well-cemented sandstones (only for the low altitude ERT line), overlying on more conductive formations associated with shales and marls. Towards south the top layer is gradually replaced by conductive formations such as shales. Therefore, the different behaviour between the sectors presented in Fig. 2b is sustained both by electrical resistivity tomography results as well by the cumulative hypsometric curves (Fig. 3a & 3b).

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